

1 **Water Vapor Vertical Distribution on Mars after Six**
2 **Years of TGO/NOMAD Solar Occultations. Part I:**
3 **Global Climatology**

4 **A. Brines¹, M. A. López-Valverde¹, B. Funke¹, F. González-Galindo¹,**
5 **S. Aoki^{2,3}, I. R. Thomas², G. L. Villanueva⁴, G. Liuzzi⁵, J. T. Erwin²,**
6 **U. Grabowski⁶, F. Forget⁷, J. J. Lopez-Moreno¹, J. Rodriguez-Gomez¹,**
7 **F. Daerden², L. Trompet², B. Ristic², M. R. Patel⁸, J. A. Holmes⁸,**
8 **G. Bellucci⁹, A. Modak¹⁰ and A. C. Vandaele²**

9 ¹Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía (IAA/CSIC), Spain

10 ²Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy, Belgium

11 ³Department of Complexity Science and Engineering, University of Tokyo, Japan

12 ⁴NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, USA

13 ⁵University of Basilicata, Italy

14 ⁶Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research, Karlsruhe, Germany

15 ⁷Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique, IPSL, Paris, France

16 ⁸Open University, UK

17 ⁹Istituto di Astrofisica e Planetologia, Italy

18 ¹⁰Institute for Basic Science, South Korea

19 **Key Points:**

- 20 • Three complete Martian Years of water vapor vertical distribution from Mars' troposphere
21 to mesopause using infrared solar occultations.
- 22 • More vertically extended water vapor abundances during perihelion seasons compared
23 to aphelion as a result of Mars' orbital eccentricity.
- 24 • Overall larger abundances and enhanced vertical transport are observed during
25 evening observations, compared to morning measurements.

Corresponding author: Adrián Brines, adrianbm@iaa.es

Abstract

We present vertical profiles of water vapor obtained during six continuous years of solar occultation observations in the infrared by the NOMAD instrument on board TGO. The retrievals have been performed with an inversion code previously applied to smaller samples of this data set, but improved to combine pairs of diffraction orders allowing for sounding water vapor up to about 120 km altitude. As a first part of a set of two papers, this study presents the most extended data set of water vapor measurements from the NOMAD instrument to date, covering three full and consecutive Martian Years. Building upon previous researches primarily focused on the perihelion season, this analysis now includes the aphelion season, offering a comprehensive view of Mars' water cycle. Observations from April 2018 to December 2023 were analyzed, covering perihelion of Mars Year (MY) 34 to aphelion of MY 37 and presenting water vapor vertical profiles from approximately 5-10 km to 110-120 km in altitude. This study reveals consistent seasonal and latitudinal water vapor patterns, showing water vapor systematically more vertically extended during the perihelion season than during the aphelion. We present an extensive analysis of the water vapor local time variability, confirming overall larger abundances during the evenings than during mornings. These data provide new insights into the vertical distribution of atmospheric water vapor on Mars, aiding future comparisons and global climate model validation.

Plain Language Summary

Here we study water vapor in Mars' atmosphere, a key element for understanding the planet's climate and its evolution from a once warmer, wetter world to the cold, dry planet it is today. Although Mars currently has relatively small amounts of water vapor in the atmosphere, this vapor significantly influences surface and atmospheric processes, shaping the planet's complex water cycle. Using the NOMAD instrument on the Trace Gas Orbiter (TGO), we analyzed infrared spectra taken from April 2018 to December 2023, spanning different seasons and times of day over three complete Martian years. We found that water vapor extends to higher altitudes during Mars' warmer season compared to the colder season. Additionally, water vapor was generally more abundant during the evenings than in the mornings. This work presents the most extensive data set on Mars' water vapor vertical distribution, providing a more comprehensive view of how water vapor varies across time and location on the planet.

1 Introduction

Among many other open research fields, the presence of water vapor in the Martian atmosphere stands out as a particularly engaging topic of study. This species on Mars, despite its relative low abundance, provides critical clues about the planet's climate. Water vapor participates actively on many surface and atmospheric processes such as regolith-atmosphere interactions, chemistry and photochemistry, nucleation, sublimation and transport. Its distribution throughout the planet depends, directly or indirectly, on those processes resulting in a complex water cycle also strongly coupled with temperature variations, and therefore, on the atmospheric dynamics at local and global scales. Understanding the dynamics, sources, and variability of water vapor in the Martian atmosphere nowadays and through time is essential for piecing together the planet's geological and atmospheric evolution, which has driven Mars from a more humid and warmer past to the colder and dryer planet we observe today. Despite its importance, the knowledge about the vertical distribution of water vapor in the Martian atmosphere was limited until recent years. Most of the information about water vapor available today comes from nadir sounders like the Thermal Emission Spectrometer (TES) onboard Mars Global Surveyor (MGS) (Smith, 2002, 2004) and models (Forget et al., 1999; Haberle et al., 2019). The description of water vapor in the vertical was very necessary but it requires limb sounding capabilities, and ideally, a solar occultation strategy, widely used on Earth for atmospheric sounding. This

76 technique has allowed us to achieve sensitivities high enough to study the precise vertical
77 distribution of water vapor, among other trace species.

78 The first Solar occultations on Mars focused on water vapor were performed by the
79 Auguste experiment during the Phobos mission (Rodin et al., 1997). They reported vertical
80 profiles during northern spring equinox, showing a sharp decrease in abundance above
81 25 km and confirming the presence of an hygropause at 30 km. Mars experiences significant
82 changes in temperature and pressure with latitude and season, which affects the sublimation-
83 condensation of water ice and the vertical and meridional transport of water vapor. This
84 variability means that a comprehensive understanding of the water cycle requires continuous
85 and systematic monitoring over extended periods, a milestone that could not be achieved
86 with short-term missions.

87 The Spectroscopy for the Investigation of the Characteristics of the Atmosphere
88 of Mars (SPICAM) onboard Mars Express (MEX) was the first instrument in orbit around
89 Mars with the ability to systematically use the solar occultation technique. Early studies
90 with this instrument provided water vapor vertical profiles from about 15 to 50 km which
91 were used as an indicator of an atmosphere of about 5 K warmer than predictions by Global
92 Circulation Models (GCMs) at those altitudes (Fedorova et al., 2009). In addition, SPICAM
93 found that supersaturation (saturation ratio exceeding 1) was persistent in the Martian
94 atmosphere during the northern spring-summer seasons, precisely during solar longitudes
95 (L_S) ranging from 50° to 120° (Maltagliati et al., 2011). It also revealed observations-
96 GCM discrepancies in the abundance of water above 30 km. Similar studies carried out
97 for the full Martian Year (MY) showed the importance of the vertical distribution on the
98 water water cycle. SPICAM also reported for the first time larger abundances and more
99 vertically extended profiles during the perihelion than during the aphelion season, which
100 were unexpected based on the previous knowledge of column density measurements (Maltagliati
101 et al., 2013). In addition, the analysis of observations during the MY's 28 global dust
102 storm showed that water vapor was present at altitudes up to 80 km with abundances
103 larger than 100 ppm (Fedorova et al., 2018). More recently, Fedorova et al. (2021) presented
104 another relevant SPICAM result, showing water vapor density profiles for MYs 28 to 34
105 and confirming the impact of dust storms on water vapor vertical distribution at middle
106 and high altitudes, adding to the impact of the perihelion season on the hydrogen escape
107 rates.

108 In April 2018, the Trace Gas Orbiter (TGO) started its regular science operations.
109 With several solar occultation instruments onboard such as the Nadir and Occultation
110 for Mars Discovery (NOMAD, (Vandaele et al., 2018)) and the Atmospheric Chemistry
111 Suite (ACS, (Korablev et al., 2018)), the orbital configuration of TGO makes this spacecraft
112 suitable to monitor the Martian atmosphere with an excellent sampling in the vertical
113 and a good latitudinal and seasonal coverage. To date, many studies have been carried
114 out with NOMAD and ACS, reporting outstanding results since the beginning of the mission
115 revealing valuable information about the vertical structure and variability of the Martian
116 atmosphere. To mention a few, the 2018 Global Dust Storm (GDS) was extensively discussed
117 by several teams, confirming to have a strong impact on the the water vertical distribution
118 (Aoki et al., 2019; Vandaele et al., 2019; Brines et al., 2023; Fedorova et al., 2020). Global
119 dust storms allow water vapor to be present at high altitudes and prevent its condensation
120 due to the enhanced radiative heating (Neary et al., 2020). The high sensitivity of those
121 instruments allowed for the study of water isotopic fractionation (G. L. Villanueva et al.,
122 2022), which revealed the prevalence of the perihelion season for the formation of atomic
123 hydrogen and deuterium at high altitudes (Alday et al., 2021). Also, a few recent studies
124 devoted to the perihelion season characterized the upper atmosphere's water distribution,
125 reporting water vapor abundances for the first time at altitudes as high as $\sim 100 - 120$
126 km (Belyaev et al., 2021; Brines et al., 2024).

127 Here, we present the largest NOMAD water vapor data set measured with the Solar
128 Occultation channel (SO) studied up to date. Building upon our previous water vapor

129 retrievals mainly focused on the perihelion season (Brines et al., 2023, 2024), we extended
 130 the analysis to the aphelion season providing a complete view of the Martian water cycle
 131 throughout 3 complete Martian years. We have also improved our water vapor retrieval
 132 scheme in several directions as detailed below. We analyzed almost six years of NOMAD
 133 observations from April 2018 to December 2023, ranging from $L_S = 160^\circ$ of MY 34
 134 to $L_S = 160^\circ$ of MY 37. As a first part of two-part series of papers, this data set allowed
 135 us to explore the seasonal and latitudinal variability of water vapor for three full MYs,
 136 revealing distinct patterns that repeat every year in addition to features observed only
 137 during specific years. Although a solar occultation experiment is not ideal for local time
 138 studies, we show below how the TGO orbit permits local time analysis at some latitudes
 139 and seasons. The high sensitivity of the NOMAD instrument allowed us to obtain water
 140 vapor abundances from $\sim 5 - 10$ km up to $\sim 110 - 120$ km altitude. In addition, and
 141 being the main topic of the second part of this paper, the extensive data set used in this
 142 work permitted a robust comparison between other NOMAD and ACS results and, for
 143 the first time, the application of cluster analysis techniques to Martian water vapor vertical
 144 profiles.

145 The structure of this paper is as follows: In Section 2 we describe the details about
 146 the NOMAD instrument and the data analysis. The results and discussion about the seasonal
 147 and latitudinal variability of water vapor profiles are presented in Sections 3 and 4 respectively.
 148 Detailed figures showing the latitudinal variation of each MY are presented in the Supporting
 149 Information (SI) document. A brief discussion about water vapor local time variability
 150 is presented in 5. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the results. The comparison with NOMAD
 151 and ACS along with the cluster analysis will be presented in a future second part of this
 152 paper.

153 2 Data set and analysis

154 2.1 The NOMAD instrument

155 The NOMAD instrument is a suit of three spectrometers able to sample the Martian
 156 atmosphere in different viewing geometries and at different spectral ranges operating between
 157 0.2 to $4.3 \mu\text{m}$ covering the UV, visible and infrared (IR) regions of the spectrum (Vandaele
 158 et al., 2018). Those spectrometers are (i) the Solar Occultation (SO) channel dedicated
 159 for solar occultation measurements in the IR (2.3 - $4.3 \mu\text{m}$), (ii) the Limb Nadir and solar
 160 Occultation (LNO) covering a slightly smaller spectral range than SO (2.3 - $3.8 \mu\text{m}$) but,
 161 in contrast, able to sound the atmosphere at nadir and limb geometries, and (iii) the Ultraviolet
 162 and Visible Spectrometer (UVIS) sampling the spectral region between 200 and 650 nm
 163 and also very versatile regarding observational geometries.

164 Focusing on the SO channel, its design is based upon the Solar Occultation in the
 165 Infrared (SOIR) instrument onboard Venus Express (Bertaux et al., 2007). It uses an
 166 Echelle grating in Littrow configuration (the incident and reflected angles are equal) allowing
 167 for a spectral resolution of about $\lambda/\Delta\lambda \sim 17000$ (Neefs et al., 2015). During a typical solar
 168 occultation, NOMAD is able to sample the atmosphere every second, acquiring sets of
 169 spectra at about 1 km tangent height step. An Acousto Optical Tunable Filter (AOTF)
 170 in the optical path of the instrument is used to select up to six diffraction orders, which
 171 are measured quasi-simultaneously at every altitude. This feature is particularly useful
 172 to sample different spectral regions at different altitude ranges. By selecting proper combinations
 173 of orders, we are able to avoid optically thick spectral lines or to combine different target
 174 species, allowing flexibility and making the NOMAD instrument an excellent asset to
 175 build vertical profiles of diverse science contents with an unprecedented vertical resolution.
 176 An extended description of the NOMAD instrument was presented by Neefs et al. (2015)
 177 and the most recent instrumental characterization, in which Instituto de Astrofísica de
 178 Andalucía (IAA-CSIC) participated actively, is summarized in G. L. Villanueva et al. (2022)
 179 where major updates with respect to the early in-flight calibrations (Liuzzi et al., 2019;

180 Thomas et al., 2022) were done, particularly in the AOTF and instrumental line shape
 181 (ILS) characterization.

182 The first of these, the AOTF, is best described by an asymmetric sinc-squared function
 183 with order-dependent parameters. The main issue of these kind of instruments is that
 184 the flux coming from adjacent orders propagates to the central target order. In the end,
 185 the flux measured by the detector resulted to be a combination of the main diffraction
 186 order plus an undetermined number of adjacent orders. The second key parameter, the
 187 ILS, was found to be a double Gaussian function whose widths and separation vary through
 188 each diffraction order. The AOTF and ILS parameters used in this work are those provided
 189 by G. L. Villanueva et al. (2022), assuming that the observed radiance contains flux from
 190 the central and the first four adjacent diffraction orders.

191 The latest characterization of the NOMAD SO channel are incorporated into our
 192 team’s pre-processing and retrieval suite, a set of codes devoted to clean and invert the
 193 Level 1 calibrated transmittances supplied by the NOMAD PI team. These steps are under
 194 continuous revision and improvement, and are described in the following Section.

195 2.2 Data analysis

196 The data processing and analysis performed at IAA-CSIC with NOMAD SO measurements
 197 have been extensively described in previous works (López-Valverde et al., 2023; Brines
 198 et al., 2023, 2024). In addition, at IAA-CSIC we follow a sequential inversion pipeline
 199 where other species such as CO (Modak et al., 2023), aerosols (Stolzenbach et al., 2023)
 200 and temperature and densities (López-Valverde et al., 2023) are also retrieved using NOMAD
 201 SO spectra.

202 For this work we used Level 1 calibrated transmittances (Trompet et al., 2023) from
 203 the latest pipeline processing at the Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB)
 204 and available at (ESA, 2024b). This data, however, contains some residual systematics
 205 due to instrumental effects such as bending on the spectra and spectral shifts which need
 206 to be addressed before retrieving the vertical profiles. With that goal, at IAA-CSIC we
 207 have developed a variety of pre-processing tools designed to identify and correct for the
 208 major systematics still present in the data. In particular, two of them are: (i) the bending
 209 of the spectral continuum (baseline) and (ii) the spectral shift.

210 The residual bending, which varies from scan to scan, sometimes present variations
 211 of the transmittance through the diffraction order at a single altitude of up to ~ 0.1 . This
 212 large oscillation is not caused by dust or water ice particles or by molecular absorption
 213 bands but by variations on the temperature of the detector during the start-end of each
 214 atmospheric scan. In order to characterize its spectral shape and following a similar approach
 215 to those presented in other works analyzing NOMAD SO data (Aoki et al., 2019), we
 216 used a fourth order polynomial to fit the baseline of each spectrum. This is a common
 217 assumption by all teams working with NOMAD SO data. However, this removal needs
 218 to be done carefully since the presence of absorption lines may introduce a bias during
 219 the baseline characterization. For a precise removal, we used line-by-line forward model
 220 calculations carried out with the Karlsruhe Optimized Radiative transfer Algorithm (KOPRA,
 221 (Stiller, 2000)). This forward model has been adapted for the Martian atmosphere and
 222 more recently, updated with the NOMAD SO instrument characterization (AOTF and
 223 ILS) mentioned above. During the bending correction, the spectral shift is characterized
 224 simultaneously and eventually also corrected. The cleaning of the NOMAD SO data has
 225 been extensively described in López-Valverde et al. (2023) and Brines et al. (2023). The
 226 advantage of our methodology is that when using the KOPRA simulations we are taking
 227 into account any instrumental effects introduced into the spectra. These cautions are especially
 228 relevant for the analysis at high altitudes, where a poor characterization of the continuum
 229 can lead to large biases affecting the line depths, or for other purposes like the binning
 230 of spectra at different altitudes.

231 In addition to the cleaning, our pre-processing pipeline also provides an in-house
 232 characterization of the random component of the measurement noise using covariance
 233 matrices (C-matrix). Those matrices were computed for each solar occultation using dozens
 234 of spectra from the Top Of the Atmosphere (TOA), with their diagonals containing the
 235 random oscillations in the measurements (C-noise). This C-noise resulted to be about
 236 2-4 times smaller than the nominal measurement noise provided by (Thomas et al., 2022)
 237 at high altitudes. The largest component of this nominal value is a systematic spectrally
 238 correlated component that can be addressed during the inversion. Hence, using a much
 239 smaller random noise allowed us to improve the sensitivity of our inversions at the uppermost
 240 atmosphere (Brines et al., 2024).

241 Here we applied the IAA-CSIC processing pipeline to an extended NOMAD SO
 242 data set for water vapor, as an improved follow-up study of the work presented by Brines
 243 et al. (2023, 2024). We selected a total of 7624 occultations taken during Martian Years
 244 (MY) 34, 35, 36 and 37. These observations cover a Solar Longitude range from $L_S \sim 160^\circ$
 245 of MY 34 to $L_S \sim 160^\circ$ of MY 37, being the most extensive NOMAD SO data set up to
 246 date. In Figure 1 we show the seasonal-latitude distribution of all the occultations indicating
 247 the morning observations from 1 am to 11 am (blue) and evening observations (red) from
 248 1 pm to 11 pm.

Figure 1: Latitude of the analyzed NOMAD SO observations over solar longitude for MYs 34, 35, 36 and 37. Color indicates local solar time of the measurements, blue and red for morning and evening observations respectively. Vertical black lines indicate the beginning of each Martian Year.

249 We analyzed all the NOMAD data available in four different diffraction orders: 134
 250 ($3011\text{-}3035\text{ cm}^{-1}$), 136 ($3056\text{-}3081\text{ cm}^{-1}$), 168 ($3775\text{-}3805\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 169 ($3798\text{-}3828\text{ cm}^{-1}$).
 251 The first two contain relatively weak absorption lines ($S \sim 10^{-21}\text{ cm}^{-1}/(\text{molecule}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2})$),
 252 whereas the others show much stronger lines from the spectral region close to the ν_3 fundamental
 253 band which saturate at low altitudes (optical depth > 1). Since the AOTF allows for simultaneous
 254 measurement of different diffraction orders at each tangent height, for each occultation
 255 we can select the most convenient order at every altitude. This way we developed a strategy
 256 to combine up to four different pairs of orders, 134 or 136 with 168 or 169, using them
 257 at different altitude ranges. This methodology is possible only when both orders have
 258 been measured during the same solar occultation, and although it limits the number of
 259 occultations available, it is necessary in order to obtain reliable vertical profiles from the
 260 bottom to the top of the atmosphere. Typically, we used low altitude orders (134/136)
 261 below 60 km and high altitude orders (168/169) above 60 km. This transition altitude,
 262 however, is not fixed. We used KOPRA simulations to calculate the curve of growth (variation
 263 of the line equivalent width with number of absorbers) of the strongest lines in orders

264 168 and 169 to estimate the water vapor partial pressure where those lines became optically
 265 thick. Then, using a first, approximate estimation of the water vapor volume mixing ratio
 266 (VMR) for each scan obtained during the pre-processing (based on the linedepth of the
 267 KOPRA simulations used during the bending and shift correction), we determined the
 268 optimal transition altitude for each occultation.

269 The water vapor profiles were obtained using the Retrieval Control Program (RCP,
 270 (von Clarmann et al., 2003)), a multi-parameter non-linear least squares fitting of measured
 271 and modeled spectra, which incorporates KOPRA as its Forward Model. We followed
 272 the same methodology from our previous works (Brines et al., 2023), although with the
 273 improvements previously described in the measurement noise characterization and modifying
 274 the retrieval setup to permit the combination of orders, conducting a single global fit to
 275 data from two different diffraction orders. These improvements allowed us to obtain consistent
 276 vertical profiles for an extended vertical range from ~ 5 to ~ 120 km altitude. The lowermost
 277 altitude limit is due to the presence of aerosols, mostly suspended dust in the lower atmosphere,
 278 and varies depending on the season and location of the occultation. This bottom altitude
 279 for the inversion was determined during the pre-processing using an estimation of the
 280 slant opacity, cutting those altitudes with values of total optical depth along the line of
 281 sight larger than 2.0 (~ 0.1 in transmittance) and avoiding steep gradients larger than
 282 0.08 km^{-1} . On the other hand, the upper altitude layer for the inversion is also variable
 283 with season and location and was set during the inversion using the averaging kernels
 284 computed during the retrieval. As done by Brines et al. (2023), here we also filter low
 285 values of averaging kernels, i.e., we exclude some retrievals with low information content,
 286 typically with too weak absorption lines (below measurement noise), in order to avoid
 287 water abundances biased towards the a priori/climatology. During the inversions, for the
 288 a priori atmosphere we used pressure and temperature profiles extracted from specific
 289 runs of the Mars Planetary Climate Model (Mars-PCM, (Forget et al., 1999)) at the exact
 290 time and location of each solar occultation. The Mars-PCM runs were performed taking
 291 into account the best estimate of the dust optical depths from Montabone et al. (2020)
 292 for each MY, including the GDS in MY 34. Due to the lack of measured data, for MY
 293 37 we used the same dust climatology than for MY 36. Since only the aphelion season
 294 of MY 37 ($L_S < 160^\circ$) is analyzed here, corresponding to a period of low dust activity,
 295 we expect this climatology and Mars-PCM simulation to have a negligible impact on our
 296 results. In this regard, we recall that our inversions are highly independent on the assumed
 297 thermal structure. We used a first order Tikhonov regularization optimized for each diffraction
 298 order, first determined by performing synthetic retrievals and then fine tuned with a subset
 299 of actual inversions, which allowed us to select a regularization as a trade off between
 300 error propagation, vertical resolution and convergence rate.

301 Besides the propagation of the uncertainty in the measured transmittance during
 302 the inversion, we need to take into account and quantify other sources of errors: (i) the
 303 uncertainty in the reference atmosphere and (ii) uncertainty in the NOMAD instrumental
 304 calibration. We performed several sensitivity tests introducing modification on the a priori
 305 atmosphere, varying the temperature by ± 5 K (estimated accuracy of our dedicated runs
 306 of the Mars-PCM) and introducing wave functions to simulate extreme $\pm 10\%$ oscillations
 307 in the pressure. These tests gave an uncertainty in the retrieved water vapor volume mixing
 308 ratio (VMR) of about 5%. Regarding the instrumental calibration, the major uncertainty
 309 comes from the AOTF characterization. We performed retrievals varying the AOTF parameters
 310 by 1σ , which resulted in impacts of about $\pm 10\%$ in the retrieved water vapor VMR. These
 311 uncertainties have to be taken into account when analyzing the results and during the
 312 comparisons with other teams.

313 Our processing and inversion scheme allowed us to successfully retrieve a total of
 314 7558 water vapor vertical profiles, which are analyzed next.

315 3 Seasonal variability

316 The results of our retrievals, applied to the database mentioned in the previous section,
 317 are presented in Figure 2 and can be found in the public data repository (Brines et al.,
 318 2025). Water vapor VMR cross-sections at 30 km and 80 km altitude are shown in 2-a
 319 and 2-b respectively. The vertical variation of the water vapor profiles during all the analyzed
 320 MYs are shown in Figures 2-c and 2-d for the northern and southern hemispheres respectively.
 321 For visualization purposes in Figures 2-a and 2-b, we averaged the water vapor VMR
 322 measured within ± 5 km altitude windows and within boxes of 5° in latitude and 5°
 323 in solar longitude. In Figures 2-c and 2-d we performed a weighted average of the profiles
 324 within bins of 1° in solar longitude. The latitude where each solar occultation was performed
 325 shown in the top panels exhibits a relatively quick variation from low to high latitudes
 326 (and vice versa). This peculiarity of the TGO orbit makes these maps difficult to analyze
 327 due to the fact that season, latitude and local time are linked, i.e., changing simultaneously.
 328 Nevertheless, this representation allows for the identification of several climatological patterns,
 329 repeated year after year, and it allows to highlight specific distinct events. Hereafter, and
 330 for the benefit of the reader, we will use the notation L_S^X when referring to the solar longitude
 331 of the MY X .

Figure 2: Vertical distribution of water vapor volume mixing ratio (VMR) over Solar Longitude during MYs 34, 35, 36 and 37 for the Northern (c) and Southern (d) hemispheres. Notice that the water vapor abundance's color scale is not linear. Top panel indicates the Latitude and H_2O VMR at 30 (a) and 80 (b) km altitude. Color arrows in the x axis indicate specific climatological features (see text for details).

332

3.1 Northern hemisphere

333

334

335

336

337

338

339

340

341

342

343

344

345

346

When looking at the Northern hemisphere we observe that water vapor is more abundant at two altitude ranges depending on the season. During the perihelion season of each MY ($L_S \sim 180^\circ - 360^\circ$), water vapor presents large abundances (above 60 ppm) from about 10 km or below, up to 60 km. In particular, during $L_S^{34} \sim 190^\circ - 210^\circ$ we observe a distinct enhancement of the water abundance of about 60-80 ppm at 70 km, reaching up to ~ 20 ppm at 80 km. The ultimate source of this feature (indicated with a green arrow in the x axis in Figure 2) during MY 34 was the GDS, and this abundance is not observed again with such intensity during the rest of the data set. The large dust abundance present in the atmosphere during that period lead to an increase of the temperature in the 40-60 km altitude range (Neary et al., 2020) which prevented the condensation of water vapor at those altitudes. As a consequence, water was able to be present in form of vapor at higher altitudes than usual. This topic was extensively discussed by previous works analyzing NOMAD data such as Aoki et al. (2019); Brines et al. (2023) and also by other TGO instruments like ACS NIR (Fedorova et al., 2020).

347

348

349

350

351

352

353

354

355

356

357

358

At the end of each Martian year, a regional dust storm, known as C-storm (Kass et al., 2016), usually occurs. So far, for MYs 34 to 36 those storms occurred at $L_S^{34} \sim 330^\circ$, $L_S^{35} \sim 318$ and $L_S^{36} \sim 314$ with typical dust extinctions ranging from 0.0014 to 0.0020 km^{-1} (Martín-Rubio et al., 2024). In this type of storms, the top-most altitude where dust was observed was about 60 km in the southern hemisphere with maximum abundances of about 25 ppm at 40 km, in contrast to the ~ 75 km top-most altitude and abundance peak of 70 ppm observed during the GDS (Liuzzi et al., 2020). Since these late-year dust event repeat every year, we cannot compare the water vapor response to it with a year without C-storm. Nevertheless, the seasonally decreasing water vapor abundances in the northern hemisphere during this period shows a reversed trend when the C-storms occur, with increased abundances below 60 km at $L_S^{34} \sim 330^\circ$, $L_S^{35} \sim 320^\circ$ and $L_S^{36} \sim 330^\circ$ (indicated with pink arrows in the x axis in Figure 2).

359

360

361

362

363

364

Unfortunately, the top most altitude where water is observed during the perihelion is forced to 120 km by the NOMAD sampling, which only provides spectra up to this altitude for the water vapor diffraction orders analyzed in this study. Although it might be signatures of water vapor in the spectra, with the current data any information obtained from above 120 km comes mainly from the a priori climatology used during the retrieval process. For that reason we limited our analysis to this altitude.

365

366

367

368

369

370

371

372

On the other hand, during the aphelion season ($L_S \sim 0^\circ - 180^\circ$) large water vapor abundances (above 60 ppm) seem to be more confined to low altitudes, from 5 km to 10 km, showing a sharp decrease at 20-30 km. In addition, the top most altitude where water was detected during this period falls from 120 km observed during the perihelion to a tangent height of about 80 km. This period corresponds to the northern summer, so the large abundance observed in the lower atmosphere corresponds to the well known summer season's water release from the sublimation of the northern polar cap due to the increase of the temperature in this hemisphere (G. L. Villanueva et al., 2022).

373

3.2 Southern hemisphere

374

375

376

377

378

379

380

381

382

The Southern hemisphere also shows distinct climatological patterns. Water is present in larger abundance and in a more extended vertical range during the perihelion season, coinciding with the southern spring and summer. During this period, also known as the "dusty season", local/regional dust storm events are frequent and the abundance of aerosols (dust) in the atmosphere is significantly larger than during other seasons. Due to its orbital eccentricity, Mars receives an enhanced solar flux at perihelion leading to a warmer southern summer (Smith et al., 2017) and an intense single cell meridional circulation, transporting species like water vapor from the south to the north. This effect is also affected by the topographic asymmetry between hemispheres, where the higher southern surface elevation

383 results in a more intense thermal forcing of the mean circulation (Barnes et al., 2017).
 384 Close to the summer solstice, around $L_S \sim 270^\circ$ a strong injection of water vapor to the
 385 mesopause (~ 100 km) is repeated every year. This feature observed at high southern latitudes
 386 (indicated with blue arrows in the x axis in Figure 2) has been discussed in previous works
 387 (G. L. Villanueva et al., 2022; Aoki et al., 2022; Fedorova et al., 2021; Belyaev et al., 2021;
 388 Brines et al., 2024) and although it is still not fully understood, some modeling efforts
 389 suggest the vertical flux of the meridional circulation combined with solar tides to be responsible
 390 of this strong water vapor pumping (Shaposhnikov et al., 2019). This, and in together
 391 with global dust storms seems to be an important mechanism for the effective injection
 392 of water vapor to thermospheric altitudes (above 100 km) affecting the thermal escape
 393 of hydrogen on Mars.

394 The southern autumn and winter seasons ($L_S \sim 0^\circ - 180^\circ$) show a clear contrast
 395 compared to the local summer. During the aphelion season, above 70-80 km the water
 396 vapor abundance is extremely low, below our detection limits matching the behavior observed
 397 in the northern hemisphere. In this case, only burst of abundances of about ~ 50 ppm
 398 below 40 km are observed occasionally at $L_S \sim 30^\circ$ and $L_S \sim 90^\circ$, corresponding to a latitudinal
 399 effect rather than seasonal trends, since these observations were taken at latitudes below
 400 30° (see Section 4). In Figure 2, these features are indicated with red arrows in the x
 401 axis.

402 4 Latitudinal variability

403 Although the interhemispheric asymmetry is evident in Fig. 2, the large seasonal
 404 variation complicates other studies, like detailed latitudinal analysis. Hence, another representation
 405 of the profiles with a careful selection of appropriate occultations is required.

406 Here we selected different subsets of observations taken during relatively small ranges
 407 of L_S ($\Delta L_S = 30^\circ$), which show a significant latitudinal sampling. For a given latitude,
 408 in order to avoid mixing observations made at different local times, we split the sets considering
 409 occultations from only one terminator (morning or evening). We present the vertical profiles
 410 within those L_S windows using latitude-altitude maps, assuming that the observed water
 411 vapor distribution is caused only by the latitudinal variability. These cautions are also
 412 needed in order to analyze effects of the local time variations, which are discussed in the
 413 next Section.

414 4.1 Aphelion season

415 In Figures 3 and 4 we show the latitudinal distribution of water vapor for the aphelion
 416 season (from $L_S = 0^\circ$ to $L_S = 180^\circ$) at the morning and evening terminators respectively.
 417 Here, the vertical profiles were averaged in 5° latitude bins. Observations from MYs 35,
 418 36 and 37 within the same L_S window were used to compute the latitudinal distribution
 419 for each panel.

420 During both the aphelion and the periods close to the equinoxes ($L_S = 0^\circ$ and
 421 $L_S = 180^\circ$), most of the water vapor is confined to altitudes below 40 km. Particularly
 422 noticeable at mid latitudes ($\sim 30^\circ$) in MYs 35 and 36 we observe abundances below
 423 20 ppm above 40 km during the evenings as shown in Figures 4-a1, 4-a2, 4-b1 and 4-b2.
 424 In contrast, during mornings, in Figures 3-a1, 3-a2, 3-b1 and 3-b2 this limit is observed
 425 at 20-30 km. During this period of the year, close to the northern spring equinox, all Martian
 426 years show a similar structure, mostly symmetric respect to the equator and with the
 427 larger water abundances appearing between 30°S - 30°N . The global meridional transport
 428 induces a polar warming in the middle atmosphere (~ 60 km) as the downward branch
 429 of the cross-equatorial circulation descends at high latitudes (Medvedev & Hartogh, 2007;
 430 McCleese et al., 2010). This effect occurs at both hemispheres since the warmest surface
 431 temperatures at the equator lead to a two-cell Hadley circulation with a low latitude upwelling

Figure 3: Latitudinal distribution of water vapor profiles during the aphelion season (from $L_S = 0^\circ$ to $L_S = 180^\circ$ of MYs 35 (top), 36 (middle) and 37 (bottom) panels) from observations at the morning terminator. Each panel spans 30° in Solar Longitude.

Figure 4: Same as Fig. 3 but for evening terminator observations.

432 branch (Smith et al., 2017) and a descent branch at high latitudes causing an adiabatic
 433 warming. These warmer polar temperatures were also reported by ACS (Fedorova et al.,
 434 2023; Belyaev et al., 2022) and could be responsible for the water vapor enhancement
 435 observed at ~ 40 km particularly evident in the southern hemisphere (30°S - 60°S), as shown
 436 in Figure 3-a1. A similar water vapor enhancement is also observed over the northern
 437 hemisphere at mid-latitudes in the evening observations, as shown in Figure 4-a1. At these
 438 high latitudes and below this layer, water vapor abundance drops and this seems to be
 439 associated to the formation of water ice clouds (Fedorova et al., 2023; Stolzenbach et al.,
 440 2023). The enhancement of water vapor abundance in the middle atmosphere at high
 441 latitudes is observed again during the period close to the northern autumn equinox, as
 442 shown in Figures 3-a6, 3-b6 for the morning and in Figures 4-a6 and 4-b6 for the evening
 443 terminator, which coincides with warm layers at polar latitudes, also observed by ACS
 444 MIR (Belyaev et al., 2022) and ACS NIR data (Fedorova et al., 2023).

445 Close to the northern summer solstice ($L_S = 90^\circ$), the equatorial symmetric pattern
 446 previously described disappears, revealing an asymmetric structure between both hemispheres,
 447 very repetitive and similar during MYs 34, 35 and 36. As shown in Figures 3-a3, 3-a4,
 448 3-b3, 3-b4, 3-c3, 3-c4 for the morning and 4-a3, 4-a4, 4-b3, 4-b4, 4-c3, 4-c4 for the evening
 449 terminator, the distribution of water vapor is shifted towards the northern hemisphere.
 450 The increase of the temperatures at high northern latitudes leads to the sublimation of
 451 the polar cap in the summer hemisphere, releasing large amounts of water resulting in
 452 low altitude (below 10 km) VMRs > 200 ppm at high latitudes $\sim 60^\circ\text{N}$. These large
 453 abundances in the northern hemisphere are more confined to lower altitudes during the
 454 mornings than during the evenings, possibly due to the temperature differences in the
 455 lower atmosphere (of about 5-10 K colder morning temperatures during this season (Fedorova
 456 et al., 2023)) and to the formation of nighttime ice clouds. Precipitation from these ice
 457 clouds at nighttime could lead to water vapor being closer to the surface in the morning
 458 (Daerden et al., 2010)

459 At the end of this first half of the year, close to the northern autumn equinox, the
 460 vertical extent of the observed water vapor abundances are significantly larger than during
 461 the spring equinox, specifically during evenings (Figure 4-b6), where VMRs > 100 ppm
 462 are present at ~ 50 km altitude in the northern hemisphere. Evening temperatures observed
 463 by ACS were larger during this period than during the northern spring equinox (Belyaev
 464 et al., 2022), possibly increasing the altitude where water ice clouds form. This is also
 465 suggested by Aoki et al. (2022) based on GEM-Mars simulations, who found this late
 466 aphelion water vapor enhancement in the northern hemisphere related to a lower rate
 467 of cloud formation during daytime.

468 Finally, it is worth to mention a noticeable water vapor enhancement observed only
 469 in MY 37 at $\sim 60^\circ\text{N}$ during $L_S \sim 110^\circ$, as shown in Figure 4-c4. This kind of enhancements,
 470 showing abundances as large as 50 ppm reaching altitudes of about 60 km are rarely observed
 471 during this season at this high northern latitudes. In a preliminary analysis of this feature
 472 we have discarded it to be a bias in our retrievals, and currently ongoing work indicates
 473 that this water vapor injection to high altitudes could be related with an out-of-season
 474 dust event triggering an unprecedented water pumping. We are currently investigating
 475 this particular phenomenon and a dedicated study will be published in the future.

476 4.2 Perihelion season

477 In Figures 5 and 6 we show the latitudinal distribution of water vapor during the
 478 perihelion season (from $L_S = 180^\circ$ to $L_S = 360^\circ$) of MYs 34, 35 and 36 at the morning
 479 and evening terminators respectively. Similarly to what is shown for the aphelion season,
 480 profiles were averaged in bins of 5° latitude.

481 First, in Figures 5-a1,5-b1, 5-a1, 6-a1,6-b1,6-c1, hints of the typical equinoctial symmetric
 482 structure are visible, being significantly more intense than its aphelion analog. During
 483 this period ($L_S^{34} = 180^\circ - 210^\circ$), MY 34's GDS reached its peak and its effects are
 484 noticeable when comparing Figure 6-a1 with the same period of MYs 35 and 36 (Figures
 485 6-b1 and 6-c1 respectively). The GDS reached its mature phase at $L_S^{34} = 198^\circ$ and
 486 the peak on the temperature increase due to the large dust abundance was registered
 487 around $L_S^{34} = 207^\circ$ (Kass et al., 2020). During this period, the effects of the storm
 488 can only be observed at the evening terminator due to the sampling location and timing
 489 of NOMAD measurements, capturing the GDS during the evenings. Nevertheless, the
 490 interannual variability between MY 34 and the following years is evident. In MY 34 we
 491 observe water abundance of about 100 ppm even at 70-80 km altitude in the southern
 492 hemisphere at $\sim 60^\circ$ latitude, showing a sharp decrease towards polar latitudes at $> 80^\circ\text{S}$.
 493 In the northern hemisphere, the distribution is similar, with large abundance of about
 494 200 ppm below 40 km and again, a sharp decrease at $> 65^\circ\text{N}$. The larger abundances
 495 at high southern latitudes are possibly due to the weakening of the Southern Polar Vortex

Figure 5: Latitudinal distribution of water vapor profiles during the aphelion season (from $L_S = 180^\circ$ to $L_S = 360^\circ$ of MYs 34 (top), 35 (middle) and 36 (bottom) panels) from observations at the morning terminator. Each panel spans 30° in Solar Longitude.

Figure 6: Same as Fig. 5 but for evening terminator observations.

496 induced by the storm (Streeter et al., 2021). During non-GDS years the abundance at
 497 latitudes $> 60^\circ\text{S}$ was not larger than 20 ppm as shown in Figures 6-b1 and 6-c1.

498 After the GDS, during its decay phase at $L_S^{34} = 213 - 230^\circ$ (Kass et al., 2020),
 499 the interannual variability is more noticeable in the northern hemisphere. In Figures 5-
 500 a2 and 6-a2, for both terminators morning and evening terminators respectively, at latitudes
 501 $0^\circ\text{N}-30^\circ\text{N}$ we observe water abundance of about 100 ppm at 50 km during MY 34, whereas
 502 in the following years this values are observed only below 20-30 km (Figures 5-b2, 5-c2,
 503 6-b2 and 6-c2). In contrast, in the southern hemisphere at latitudes $> 60^\circ\text{S}$ we notice
 504 larger abundances below 60 km at the evening terminator during the years without GDS,
 505 with at least 100 ppm. These differences between years with and without global dust storms
 506 were reported by Brines et al. (2024), and Pankine et al. (2023) found systematically lower
 507 water vapor abundance at high southern latitudes during the years with storms compared
 508 to the years with regular dust activity.

509 For the following sets between $L_S = 240^\circ - 300^\circ$ the distribution and abundance
 510 of water below 60 km is similar in all the three MYs, although MY 34 shows lower abundances
 511 particularly during morning observations, as shown in Figures 5-a3, 5-b3 and 5-c3, feature
 512 already reported by Brines et al. (2024).

513 In Figures 5-a3, 5-a4, 5-b3, 5-b4, 5-c3, 5-c4 for the morning, and 6-a3, 6-a4, 6-b3,
 514 6-b4, 6-c3, 6-c4 for the evening terminator, we observe an asymmetric pattern with more
 515 vertically extended abundance in the southern hemisphere and repeated systematical-
 516 ly every year. This is possibly due as a result of the vertical transport produced by the
 517 upwelling branch of the Hadley cell, which intensifies during southern summer due to
 518 the enhancement of the solar flux produced by the orbital eccentricity of Mars and also
 519 to the north-south topography dichotomy (Richardson & Wilson, 2002). Above 60 km,
 520 however, some interannual differences arise. MYs 35 and 36 present a large injection of
 521 water vapor to the upper atmosphere particularly intense at the evening terminator and
 522 only at mid-high southern latitudes, the larger enhancement being located at $50^\circ\text{S}-60^\circ\text{S}$.
 523 We observe abundances of about 50 ppm up to 100 km as shown in Figures 6-b3 and 6-
 524 c3, feature which appears later and with reduced intensity in MY 34 (Figure 6-a4). This
 525 observed plume, reported by ACS (Belyaev et al., 2021) and NOMAD (Aoki et al., 2022;
 526 G. L. Villanueva et al., 2022), was recently deeply analyzed by Brines et al. (2024), who
 527 presented an extended discussion about the nature of this phenomena and suggested long
 528 term effects of the GDS to be responsible of its weak and delayed appearance during MY
 529 34. During this same period ($L_S = 240^\circ - 300^\circ$), at the northern hemisphere we observe
 530 a layer of low water vapor abundance below 20 ppm at 40-60 km. This depletion of water
 531 seems to be present at both terminators although is particularly noticeable at the morning
 532 terminator in Figure 5 and, where water increases again above the depletion, forming
 533 another layer of $> 20\text{ppm}$ visible at ~ 100 km (Figures 5-b4 and 5-c4). On one hand,
 534 these layers of depleted water vapor coincide with regions where water ice clouds were
 535 observed by Fedorova et al. (2023). On the other hand, the presence of larger abundance
 536 above, as discussed in the following section, suggests either a more efficient northward
 537 transport through the meridional circulation at high altitudes during mornings than during
 538 evenings, or sublimation of the water ice clouds below due to the presence of a morning
 539 warm layer at ~ 80 km (Fedorova et al., 2023).

540 As discussed in the previous section, the last part of the year is particularly interesting
 541 due to the frequent occurrence of C-Storms. These dust events warmed up the atmosphere
 542 and their effects allowing water vapor to reach higher altitudes can be observed more clearly
 543 at the evening terminator in Figures 6-a5 and 6-b5 for MYs 34 and 35 respectively. These
 544 years show larger water vapor abundance in a more extended vertical range (up to 60-
 545 70 km) at high southern latitudes ($\sim 60^\circ$). These regions were sampled by NOMAD during
 546 most of the duration of the C-Storm in MY 34 and during the decay phase of the storm
 547 in My 35. Interestingly, the effects on the water vapor are not so evident at these high
 548 southern latitudes in MY 36 (Figure 6-c5), with lower abundances at 40-60 km compared
 549 to previous years during the same period. The reason of this difference is mostly due to
 550 the NOMAD sampling. The C-Storm in MY 36 started at $L_S \sim 308^\circ$ and lasted until
 551 $L_S \sim 320^\circ$ (Martín-Rubio et al., 2024). During this period, unfortunately only few
 552 observations were available from NOMAD, most of them taken only at $L_S 309^\circ$ at mid
 553 latitudes and missing the peak and decay phase of this storm. This observational bias
 554 limits the characterization of the storm effects on water vapor during MY 36. Just 1°
 555 in solar longitude after the starting of this storm might not be enough to reveal relevant
 556 enhancements on the water vapor global circulation. Additionally, at the end of the year,
 557 the larger abundances observed in MY 34 (Figure 5-a6) compared to the following ones
 558 (Figures 5-b6 and 5-c6) particularly in the morning terminator could also be attributed
 559 to effects of the C-Storm in MY 34. This year, unlike MYs 35 and 36, the storm triggered
 560 later in time and lasted for a longer period ranging from $L_S 319^\circ$ to $L_S 340^\circ$ (Martín-
 561 Rubio et al., 2024).

5 Local time variability

Figure 7: Multi-annual average of longitude-altitude distribution of NOMAD SO water vapor Volume Mixing Ratio (VMR) in 55° - 65° at the northern (left) and southern (right) hemispheres. (a1 and a2) Northern’s hemisphere longitudinal distribution at $L_S = 60^{\circ} - 90^{\circ}$ during morning and evening respectively. (b1 and b2) Southern’s hemisphere longitudinal distribution at $L_S = 105^{\circ} - 135^{\circ}$ during morning and evening respectively. (c1 and c2) Northern’s hemisphere longitudinal distribution at $L_S = 270^{\circ} - 300^{\circ}$ during morning and evening respectively. (d1 and d2) Southern’s hemisphere longitudinal distribution at $L_S = 240^{\circ} - 270^{\circ}$ during morning and evening respectively. For each longitudinal map, left panel shows averaged profiles at longitudes 180° W- 90° W (blue), 90° W- 0° (orange), 0° - 90° E (green) and 90° E- 180° E (red). Errorbars indicate the standard deviation within each longitude interval.

563 The selection of the L_S ranges in Figures 3, 4 5 and 6 was made in order to allow
 564 for the interannual comparison throughout different seasons. Although morning and
 565 terminator are clearly differentiated, not all latitudes and longitudes were sampled at
 566 both terminators for all the profile sets. For each TGO orbit, typically NOMAD measures
 567 a sunrise and a sunset at each hemisphere, thus making the analysis of local time variations
 568 complicated. Despite this limitation, the TGO orbital geometry allows for the sampling
 569 of nearby latitudes and longitudes at both terminators during a few L_S ranges throughout
 570 the Martian year. For this Section we selected another subset of profiles in some L_S intervals

Figure 8: Vertical profiles showing the ratios morning/evening at $L_S = 60^\circ - 90^\circ$ (a), $L_S = 270^\circ - 300^\circ$ (b) for the northern hemisphere and $L_S = 105^\circ - 135^\circ$ (c) and $L_S = 240^\circ - 270^\circ$ (d) for the southern hemisphere. For each panel, the color indicates the longitudinal range where the ratio was computed: $180^\circ\text{W}-90^\circ\text{W}$ (blue), $90^\circ\text{W}-0^\circ$ (orange), $0^\circ-90^\circ\text{E}$ (green) and $90^\circ\text{E}-180^\circ\text{E}$ (red). Errorbars indicate the uncertainty due to the variability within each longitude interval.

571 not larger than 30° in order to avoid seasonal variability effects as much as possible. We
 572 selected a total four L_S windows, two for each hemisphere. In order to allow for a comprehensive
 573 analysis of local time variations these sets of observations allow the comparison of similar
 574 latitudes and longitudes during the morning and evening. The most common local times
 575 of NOMAD SO observations are 6am and 6pm for the morning and evening respectively.
 576 For this study we consider morning (evening) observations all those measured at $6\text{am} \pm 5\text{h}$
 577 ($6\text{pm} \pm 5\text{h}$). With this restriction, morning and evening observations are separated by at
 578 least 2h during midday (midnight), and observations from 11am to 1pm (11pm to 1am)
 579 are excluded. The selected L_S windows are scattered through the year, covering the aphelion
 580 and perihelion seasons on both hemispheres. For each L_S window we obtained the water

581 vapor longitudinal distribution of averaged profiles during MYs 35 and 36 within longitude
 582 bins of 5° , at the morning and evening terminators. The distributions were obtained at
 583 latitudes between 55° - 65° in each hemisphere, where the majority of the NOMAD observations
 584 are taken. In Figure 7 we the longitude-altitude maps representative for the aphelion (four
 585 top panels) and perihelion (bottom four panels) seasons on the northern (left panels) and
 586 southern (right panels) hemispheres. In order to asses possible longitudinal variability,
 587 known to be particularly relevant at low altitudes (Pankine, 2022; Smith, 2002), for each
 588 longitudinal map we added a second panel showing the averaged water vapor profiles within
 589 regions of 90° in longitude. Despite some variability in the longitudinal distribution, larger
 590 during the second half of the year, these 90° longitudinal averages show similar vertical
 591 structures during all the selected L_S windows. The strong longitudinal variability discussed
 592 by Pankine (2022) and (Smith, 2002) apply for water vapor integrated columns, extremely
 593 sensitive to the very first few kilometers above the surface. Our retrieved profiles suggest
 594 an homogeneous water vapor vertical distribution throughout the planet at 55° - 65° in
 595 both hemispheres above 10-20 km, region that barely contributes to the estimation of
 596 the water vapor columns. In Figure 8 we show the ratio between morning and evening
 597 averaged profiles for each L_S window and 90° longitudinal bin from Figure 7.

598 Focusing first on the aphelion season, Figures 7-a1 and 7-a2 reveal a similar water
 599 vapor distribution in the northern hemisphere during both morning and evening above
 600 40 km, with four to five times larger evening water abundances at ~ 30 k at some longitudes,
 601 as shown in Figure 8-a. In contrast, the larger differences between dawn and dusk water
 602 vapor profiles are observed in the southern hemisphere. Figure 7-b1 show a layer with
 603 the largest water vapor abundances of about 5 ppm at 30-50 km altitude during the morning.
 604 This homogeneous structure around the planet becomes thicker by the end of the day,
 605 ranging from 20 up to 80 km altitude during the evening as shown in 7-b2. This leads
 606 to more than ten times larger abundances at 60-80 km during the evening than during
 607 the morning, as shown in Figure 8-c. Colder southern nighttime temperatures leading
 608 to water condensation during nights could be the driving process of these diurnal differences.
 609 This is supported by models, which show clouds typically forming at these altitudes during
 610 the aphelion season (Montmessin et al., 2004).

611 During the perihelion season, at 55° N- 65° N, the largest longitudinal variations are
 612 observed at 40-70 km altitude as shown in Figures 7-c1 and 7-c2, for the morning and
 613 evening terminators respectively. This altitude region corresponds with a minimum in
 614 the water vapor abundance and correlates with the region with the lowest temperatures
 615 during this season and latitude (Fedorova et al., 2023). In addition, those low temperatures
 616 also show prominent longitudinal variations (Fedorova et al., 2023), which might be the
 617 reason of the observed variations in water vapor. Interestingly, at these altitudes the lowest
 618 water vapor abundances are observed at 150° W- 120° W and 30° E- 90° E during the morning
 619 but only at 150° W- 90° W during the evening.

620 The contrast between northern morning and evening becomes more noticeable during
 621 this season than during the aphelion. In Figure 8-c, although below 40 km the water abundances
 622 are similar at both terminators, a clear evening enhancement at 40-80 km arises, particularly
 623 at the longitudes with the lowest water vapor abundances. Higher up, at ~ 100 km the
 624 situation reverses revealing a morning enhancement systematically at almost every longitude
 625 within latitudes between 55° N- 65° N. A tentative explanation for the presence of this layer
 626 could be the following: Water ice clouds form after sunset and during nighttime (Smith,
 627 2019) and are observed later in the morning at altitudes 60-80 km (Stcherbinine et al.,
 628 2022). This water ice cloud layer correlate with the depleted layer of water vapor observed
 629 in Figure 7-c1 in. At morning, a warm layer at 80-90 km (Fedorova et al., 2023) may sublimate
 630 the top of the clouds. This temperature inversion could prevent water vapor to immediately
 631 reach lower altitudes, confining the water vapor at high altitudes. During daytime, this
 632 warm layer descends dissipating the water ice clouds and reaching 40-60 km at the evening

(Fedorova et al., 2023). This more isothermal vertical structure allows a more homogeneous water vapor vertical distribution, as observed in Figure 7-c2.

Besides the wave effect on temperature, we can not discard additional processes like daytime photo-dissociation to play a role in this high altitude morning-evening difference. At this season (northern winter) water vapor in the northern hemisphere is supplied from the southern one via meridional transport, particularly strong during this season (Shaposhnikov et al., 2019). Water vapor photolysis rate during $L_S \sim 270^\circ$ is about $4\text{-}5 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Alday et al., 2021), more than one order of magnitude larger than during the aphelion season. This water vapor destruction rate has to be compared with the refilling by the global circulation at these high altitudes during both, daytime and nighttime. This is a complicated task and existing literature does not provide enough clues to estimate reliable water meridional fluxes at these latitudes, altitudes and season. For that reason, this exercise has to be preformed mostly with GCMs. Unfortunately, our simulations from the MPCM do not predict such water vapor morning enhancement at 100 km and studying solely our modeled northward water vapor fluxes may not be enough to confirm or discard this hypothesis. Hence, additional works have to be done, for example, by quantifying the winds and stream functions predicted by data assimilation models feed with these exact NOMAD data (Holmes et al., 2021). This task will be assessed in future publications.

In the southern hemisphere, similar to the northern one, large water vapor longitudinal variability can be observed in Figures 7-d1 and 7-d2, for the morning and evening terminators respectively. Unfortunately, the lack of data at specific longitudes do not allow to draw solid conclusions. Nevertheless, at the morning terminator, the observed distribution seems to show larger vertical water vapor extent around $150^\circ\text{W}\text{-}90^\circ\text{W}$ and $150^\circ\text{E}\text{-}90^\circ\text{E}$, with a minimum at $30^\circ\text{W}\text{-}30^\circ\text{E}$. This longitudinal wave pattern is not clear during the evening. Besides these longitudinal variations and illustrated in Figure 8-d, when averaging water vapor profiles in 90° bins a systematic trend towards larger evening abundances stands out. This being observed at all longitude bins, suggests diurnal variations to be more relevant than the longitudinal variability.

6 Discussion

Thanks to the recent missions to study Mars' atmosphere, such as ExoMars TGO, the long time needed studies focused on a systematic analysis of the vertical structure of the atmosphere are now possible. These kind of studies are essential to understand one of the main unknowns with respect to the Martian climate: the water loss. This escape process has been occurring in Mars since the last 4 billion years (G. Villanueva et al., 2015)(G. L. Villanueva et al., 2021) and it is controlled by the amount of water vapor that is able to reach high altitudes, that after being photodissociated, facilitates the escape of hydrogen to escape (Chaffin et al., 2021). On this context, recent studies have tried to characterize the water vapor distribution above 100 km and its associated escape (Belyaev et al., 2021; Brines et al., 2024). These studies focused the analysis on the perihelion season and in the southern hemisphere where the larger temperatures and hence, the stronger vertical transport, are expected. One of the most striking results of the work presented here is the potential contribution not only of the southern but also of the northern hemisphere to the water escape. The large water abundances observed at high altitudes and at high northern latitudes in the morning, if present during the whole day time period, could be extremely relevant for the total budget of hydrogen prone to escape to space. NOMAD and ACS instruments onboard TGO now permit the study of this upper regions of the atmosphere and systematically correlating water with temperature and aerosol observations will be essential for constraining the processes going on at these altitudes. Additionally, the unexpected water increase in the northern hemisphere during the aphelion of MY 37 reported here, might highlight the necessity to consider the contribution of the northern summer season to the hydrogen escape processes. This interesting event requires further analysis, not only with NOMAD observations, but also with additional limb observations from the Mars

685 Climate Sounder (MCS), which can provide temperature and aerosols extinction (Clancy
 686 et al., 2012), and observations from the Emirates Mars Ultraviolet Spectrometer (EMUS),
 687 onboard the Emirates Mars Mission (EMM), which can provide hydrogen density at the
 688 exobase (Holsclaw et al., 2021). Such cross-mission analysis will be performed and presented
 689 in future publications.

690 7 Summary and conclusions

691 For this work, we analyzed NOMAD SO spectra from more than 7,000 occultations
 692 collected over MYs 34 to 37, covering four diffraction orders and combining them to avoid
 693 extremely optically thick conditions (or saturated absorption lines). Our pre-processing
 694 pipeline significantly improved the correction of systematic errors in the NOMAD SO
 695 data compared to previous analyses (Brines et al., 2023), particularly for high-altitude
 696 measurements where accurate baseline characterization is crucial. This improvement enabled
 697 the consistent retrieval of extended water vapor vertical profiles ranging from approximately
 698 5 km to 120 km altitude during a single solar occultation.

699 In this study, we present the seasonal and latitudinal variability of water vapor in
 700 the Martian atmosphere as well as a detailed analysis of the water vapor local time variability.
 701 We provide the most extensive water vapor climatology to date based on NOMAD observations,
 702 showing strong seasonal variations in water vapor distribution on Mars. Distinct differences
 703 between perihelion and aphelion seasons in both hemispheres are evident, with the southern
 704 hemisphere experiencing larger and extended water vapor abundances during the southern
 705 summer. Our data reveals that these variations and interhemispheric asymmetry are influenced
 706 by factors such as dust storms, polar cap sublimation and Martian orbital eccentricity.

707 Particularly during equinoxes, water vapor is mostly confined to low altitudes and
 708 at latitudes lower than 60° - 50° , showing abundances below 20 ppm above 30 km during
 709 the mornings and above 40 km during the evenings. However, the vertical extension of
 710 this water vapor layers and its peak abundances are larger during the northern autumn
 711 than during the spring equinox. The latitudinal distribution is symmetric with respect
 712 to the equator, repeatedly during all MYs. In addition, our observations reveal a 40 km
 713 altitude layer of abundances of about 20 ppm at $\pm 60^\circ$ latitude as a consequence of the
 714 polar warming effect.

715 The effects of injecting water vapor at high altitudes are visible during different periods
 716 of the MYs analyzed here. During the GDS after the northern autumn equinox during
 717 MY 34, we observe abundances of about 80 ppm at 70 km altitude. In the period corresponding
 718 to the decay phase of the storm, and at altitudes below 60 km, we observe larger abundances
 719 during MYs 35 and 36 than during MY 34. During the perihelion, all MYs show a similar
 720 asymmetric distribution, with larger and more vertically extended abundances at the southern
 721 hemisphere. However, MY 35 and 36 show a more intense vertical transport at 60° S, injecting
 722 abundances of about 50 ppm at 100 km altitude. Moreover, during this period, we observe
 723 hints of the presence of water ice clouds in the form of depletion layers of water vapor
 724 in the northern hemisphere between 40 and 60 km altitude, as well as larger abundances
 725 observed in the morning compared to those observed in the evening at 100 km. This morning
 726 enhancement correlates with a temperature inversion layer observed just below.

727 Finally, interestingly MY 37 shows intense upward transport in the northern hemisphere
 728 at $L_S \sim 112^\circ$ which was not observed during other MYs and that seems to be related with
 729 a regional dust storm taking place during that same period.

730 All the results presented in this work extend and complement some of previous recent
 731 TGO studies on water vapor vertical profiles (Aoki et al., 2022; Belyaev et al., 2021; Brines
 732 et al., 2023, 2024), providing additional insight into morning/evening water vapor variability.

We have described in this work the major features observed in the water vapor distribution obtained. We believe these data set contain completely new insights into the vertical distribution of atmospheric water vapor on Mars, which shall foster future comparisons and shall permit validation of predictions by global climate models. A follow up work, presented as Part II, will be devoted to further studies of these NOMAD water vapor abundances, using cluster analysis techniques and with a focus on the comparison with vertical profiles from other data sets and with simulations with the Mars-PCM

Open Research Section

The NOMAD SO Level 1a calibrated data used in this work are available at the European Space Agency Planetary Science Archive (ESA, 2024b). More information about the data on the PSA can be found in the NOMAD Experiment-to-Archive Interface Control Document (ESA, 2024a). The results retrieved from the NOMAD SO measurements presented in this work are being archived and available at Brines et al. (2025).

Acknowledgments

The IAA/CSIC team acknowledges financial support from the Severo Ochoa grant CEX2021-001131-S and by grants PID2022-137579NB-I00, RTI2018-100920-J-I00 and PID2022-141216NB-I00 all funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033. A. Brines acknowledges financial support from the grant PRE2019-088355 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by 'ESF Investing in your future'. ExoMars is a space mission of the European Space Agency (ESA) and Roscosmos. The NOMAD experiment is led by the Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (IASB-BIRA), assisted by Co-PI teams from Spain (IAA-CSIC), Italy (INAF-IAPS), and the United Kingdom (Open University). This project acknowledges funding by the Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO), with the financial and contractual coordination by the ESA Prodex Office (PEA 4000103401, 4000121493), by Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MCIU) and by European funds under grants PGC2018-101836-B-I00 and ESP2017-87143-R (MINECO/FEDER), as well as by UK Space Agency through grants ST/V002295/1, ST/V005332/1, ST/Y000234/1 and ST/X006549/1 and Italian Space Agency through grant 2018-2-HH.0. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101004052. US investigators were supported by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Canadian investigators were supported by the Canadian Space Agency. This work was supported by the Institute for Basic Science (IBS-R035-C1). We want to thank M. Vals, F. Montmessin, F. Lefevre and the broad team supporting the continuous development of the Mars PCM.

References

- Alday, J., Trokhimovskiy, A., Irwin, P. G., Wilson, C. F., Montmessin, F., Lefèvre, F., ... others (2021). Isotopic fractionation of water and its photolytic products in the atmosphere of Mars. *Nature Astronomy*, 5(9), 943–950.
- Aoki, S., Vandaele, A., Daerden, F., Villanueva, G. L., Liuzzi, G., Clancy, R., ... others (2022). Global vertical distribution of water vapor on Mars: Results from 3.5 years of ExoMars-TGO/NOMAD science operations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 127(9), e2022JE007231.
- Aoki, S., Vandaele, A. C., Daerden, F., Villanueva, G. L., Liuzzi, G., Thomas, I. R., ... others (2019). Water vapor vertical profiles on Mars in dust storms observed by TGO/NOMAD. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 124(12), 3482–3497.
- Barnes, J. R., Haberle, R. M., Wilson, R. J., Lewis, S., Murphy, J. R., & Read, P. L. (2017). The Global Circulation.
- Belyaev, D. A., Fedorova, A., Trokhimovskiy, A., Alday, J., Montmessin, F.,

- 782 Korablev, O. I., ... Shakun, A. V. (2021). Revealing a high water abundance in
 783 the upper mesosphere of Mars with ACS onboard TGO. *Geophysical Research*
 784 *Letters*, *48*(10), e2021GL093411.
- 785 Belyaev, D. A., Fedorova, A. A., Trokhimovskiy, A., Alday, J., Korablev, O. I.,
 786 Montmessin, F., ... Patrakeeve, A. (2022). Thermal structure of the middle
 787 and upper atmosphere of Mars from ACS/TGO CO₂ spectroscopy. *Journal of*
 788 *Geophysical Research: Planets*, *127*(10), e2022JE007286.
- 789 Bertaux, J.-L., Nevejans, D., Korablev, O., Villard, E., Quémerais, E., Neefs, E., ...
 790 others (2007). SPICAV on Venus Express: Three spectrometers to study the
 791 global structure and composition of the Venus atmosphere. *Planetary and Space*
 792 *Science*, *55*(12), 1673–1700.
- 793 Brines, A., López-Valverde, M., Funke, B., González-Galindo, F., Aoki, S.,
 794 Villanueva, G., ... others (2024). Strong localized pumping of water vapor
 795 to high altitudes on Mars during the perihelion season. *Geophysical Research*
 796 *Letters*, *51*(14), e2023GL107224.
- 797 Brines, A., López-Valverde, M., Funke, B., González-Galindo, F., et al. (2025).
 798 Water Vapor Vertical Distribution on Mars after Six Years of TGO/NOMAD
 799 Solar Occultations. Part I: Global Climatology [Dataset]. [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14384256)
 800 [10.5281/zenodo.14384256](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14384256). doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14384256
- 801 Brines, A., López-Valverde, M., Stolzenbach, A., Modak, A., Funke, B., Galindo, F.,
 802 ... others (2023). Water vapor vertical distribution on Mars during perihelion
 803 season of MY 34 and MY 35 with ExoMars-TGO/NOMAD observations.
 804 *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, *128*(11), e2022JE007273.
- 805 Chaffin, M., Kass, D., Aoki, S., Fedorova, A., Deighan, J., Connour, K., ... others
 806 (2021). Martian water loss to space enhanced by regional dust storms. *Nature*
 807 *Astronomy*, *5*(10), 1036–1042.
- 808 Clancy, R. T., Sandor, B. J., Wolff, M. J., Smith, M. D., Lefèvre, F., Madeleine,
 809 J.-B., ... others (2012). Extensive MRO CRISM observations of 1.27 μm O₂
 810 airglow in Mars polar night and their comparison to MRO MCS temperature
 811 profiles and LMD GCM simulations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*,
 812 *117*(E11).
- 813 Daerden, F., Whiteway, J., Davy, R., Verhoeven, C., Komguem, L., Dickinson, C.,
 814 ... Larsen, N. (2010). Simulating observed boundary layer clouds on Mars.
 815 *Geophysical Research Letters*, *37*(4).
- 816 ESA. (2024a). *EAICD*. European Space Agency. ([https://archives.esac.esa](https://archives.esac.esa.int/psa/ftp/ExoMars2016/em16_tgo_nmd/document/EAICD/)
 817 [.int/psa/ftp/ExoMars2016/em16_tgo_nmd/document/EAICD/](https://archives.esac.esa.int/psa/ftp/ExoMars2016/em16_tgo_nmd/document/EAICD/))
- 818 ESA. (2024b). *PSA*. European Space Agency. ([https://archives.esac.esa.int/](https://archives.esac.esa.int/psa/)
 819 [psa/](https://archives.esac.esa.int/psa/))
- 820 Fedorova, A., Bertaux, J.-L., Betsis, D., Montmessin, F., Korablev, O., Maltagliati,
 821 L., & Clarke, J. (2018). Water vapor in the middle atmosphere of Mars during
 822 the 2007 global dust storm. *Icarus*, *300*, 440–457.
- 823 Fedorova, A., Korablev, O., Bertaux, J.-L., Rodin, A., Montmessin, F., Belyaev, D.,
 824 & Reberac, A. (2009). Solar infrared occultation observations by SPICAM
 825 experiment on Mars-Express: Simultaneous measurements of the vertical
 826 distributions of H₂O, CO₂ and aerosol. *Icarus*, *200*(1), 96–117.
- 827 Fedorova, A., Montmessin, F., Korablev, O., Lefèvre, F., Trokhimovskiy, A., &
 828 Bertaux, J.-L. (2021). Multi-annual monitoring of the water vapor vertical
 829 distribution on Mars by SPICAM on Mars Express. *Journal of Geophysical*
 830 *Research: Planets*, *126*(1), e2020JE006616.
- 831 Fedorova, A., Montmessin, F., Korablev, O., Luginin, M., Trokhimovskiy, A.,
 832 Belyaev, D. A., ... others (2020). Stormy water on Mars: the distribution and
 833 saturation of atmospheric water during the dusty season. *Science*, *367*(6475),
 834 297–300.
- 835 Fedorova, A., Montmessin, F., Trokhimovskiy, A., Luginin, M., Korablev, O., Alday,
 836 J., ... others (2023). A two-martian years survey of the water vapor saturation

- 837 state on Mars based on ACS NIR/TGO occultations. *Journal of Geophysical*
 838 *Research: Planets*, 128(1), e2022JE007348.
- 839 Forget, F., Hourdin, F., Fournier, R., Hourdin, C., Talagrand, O., Collins, M., ...
 840 Huot, J.-P. (1999). Improved general circulation models of the Martian
 841 atmosphere from the surface to above 80 km. *Journal of Geophysical Research:*
 842 *Planets*, 104(E10), 24155–24175.
- 843 Haberle, R. M., Kahre, M. A., Hollingsworth, J. L., Montmessin, F., Wilson, R. J.,
 844 Urata, R. A., ... Schaeffer, J. R. (2019). Documentation of the nasa/ames
 845 legacy mars global climate model: Simulations of the present seasonal water
 846 cycle. *Icarus*, 333, 130–164.
- 847 Holmes, J., Lewis, S., Patel, M., Chaffin, M., Cangi, E., Deighan, J., ... others (2021).
 848 Enhanced water loss from the martian atmosphere during a regional-scale dust
 849 storm and implications for long-term water loss. *Earth and Planetary Science*
 850 *Letters*, 571, 117109.
- 851 Holsclaw, G. M., Deighan, J., Almatroushi, H., Chaffin, M., Correira, J., Evans,
 852 J. S., ... others (2021). The emirates mars ultraviolet spectrometer (emus) for
 853 the emm mission. *Space Science Reviews*, 217, 1–49.
- 854 Kass, D., Kleinböhl, A., McCleese, D., Schofield, J., & Smith, M. (2016). Interannual
 855 similarity in the Martian atmosphere during the dust storm season. *Geophysical*
 856 *Research Letters*, 43(12), 6111–6118.
- 857 Kass, D., Schofield, J., Kleinböhl, A., McCleese, D., Heavens, N., Shirley, J., &
 858 Steele, L. (2020). Mars Climate Sounder observation of Mars' 2018 global dust
 859 storm. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 47(23), e2019GL083931.
- 860 Korablev, O., Montmessin, F., Trokhimovskiy, A., Fedorova, A. A., Shakun, A.,
 861 Grigoriev, A., ... others (2018). The atmospheric chemistry suite (ACS) of
 862 three spectrometers for the ExoMars 2016 trace gas orbiter. *Space Science*
 863 *Reviews*, 214, 1–62.
- 864 Liuzzi, G., Villanueva, G. L., Crismani, M. M., Smith, M. D., Mumma, M. J.,
 865 Daerden, F., ... others (2020). Strong variability of Martian water ice clouds
 866 during dust storms revealed from ExoMars Trace Gas Orbiter/NOMAD.
 867 *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 125(4), e2019JE006250.
- 868 Liuzzi, G., Villanueva, G. L., Mumma, M. J., Smith, M. D., Daerden, F., Ristic, B.,
 869 ... others (2019). Methane on Mars: New insights into the sensitivity of CH₄
 870 with the NOMAD/ExoMars spectrometer through its first in-flight calibration.
 871 *Icarus*, 321, 671–690.
- 872 López-Valverde, M. A., Funke, B., Brines, A., Stolzenbach, A., Modak, A., Hill, B.,
 873 ... others (2023). Martian atmospheric temperature and density profiles during
 874 the first year of NOMAD/TGO solar occultation measurements. *Journal of*
 875 *Geophysical Research: Planets*, 128(2), e2022JE007278.
- 876 Maltagliati, L., Montmessin, F., Fedorova, A., Korablev, O., Forget, F., & Bertaux,
 877 J.-L. (2011). Evidence of water vapor in excess of saturation in the atmosphere
 878 of Mars. *science*, 333(6051), 1868–1871.
- 879 Maltagliati, L., Montmessin, F., Korablev, O., Fedorova, A., Forget, F., Määttänen,
 880 A., ... Bertaux, J.-L. (2013). Annual survey of water vapor vertical
 881 distribution and water–aerosol coupling in the martian atmosphere observed by
 882 SPICAM/ME_x solar occultations. *Icarus*, 223(2), 942–962.
- 883 Martín-Rubio, C., Vicente-Retortillo, A., Gómez, F., & Rodríguez-Manfredi, J. (2024).
 884 Interannual variability of regional dust storms between Mars years 24 and 36.
 885 *Icarus*, 412, 115982.
- 886 McCleese, D., Heavens, N., Schofield, J., Abdou, W., Bandfield, J., Calcutt, S.,
 887 ... others (2010). Structure and dynamics of the martian lower and middle
 888 atmosphere as observed by the mars climate sounder: Seasonal variations in
 889 zonal mean temperature, dust, and water ice aerosols. *Journal of Geophysical*
 890 *Research: Planets*, 115(E12).
- 891 Medvedev, A. S., & Hartogh, P. (2007). Winter polar warmings and the meridional

- 892 transport on Mars simulated with a general circulation model. *Icarus*, 186(1),
893 97–110.
- 894 Modak, A., López-Valverde, M. A., Brines, A., Stolzenbach, A., Funke, B., González-
895 Galindo, F., . . . others (2023). Retrieval of Martian atmospheric CO vertical
896 profiles from NOMAD observations during the first year of TGO operations.
897 *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 128(3), e2022JE007282.
- 898 Montabone, L., Spiga, A., Kass, D. M., Kleinböhl, A., Forget, F., & Millour, E.
899 (2020). Martian year 34 column dust climatology from Mars climate sounder
900 observations: reconstructed maps and model simulations. *Journal of Geophysical
901 Research: Planets*, 125(8), e2019JE006111.
- 902 Montmessin, F., Forget, F., Rannou, P., Cabane, M., & Haberle, R. M. (2004). Origin
903 and role of water ice clouds in the Martian water cycle as inferred from a
904 general circulation model. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 109(E10).
- 905 Neary, L., Daerden, F., Aoki, S., Whiteway, J., Clancy, R. T., Smith, M., . . . others
906 (2020). Explanation for the increase in high-altitude water on Mars observed
907 by NOMAD during the 2018 global dust storm. *Geophysical Research Letters*,
908 47(7), e2019GL084354.
- 909 Neefs, E., Vandaele, A. C., Drummond, R., Thomas, I. R., Berkenbosch, S.,
910 Clairquin, R., . . . others (2015). NOMAD spectrometer on the ExoMars
911 trace gas orbiter mission: part 1—design, manufacturing and testing of the
912 infrared channels. *Applied optics*, 54(28), 8494–8520.
- 913 Pankine, A. A. (2022). Martian atmospheric water vapor abundances in my26-30 from
914 mars express pfs/lw observations. *Icarus*, 379, 114975.
- 915 Pankine, A. A., Leung, C., Tamppari, L., Martinez, G., Giuranna, M., Piqueux, S.,
916 . . . Trokhimovskiy, A. (2023). Effects of global dust storms on water vapor in
917 the southern polar region of Mars. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*,
918 128(12), e2023JE008016.
- 919 Richardson, M. I., & Wilson, R. J. (2002). A topographically forced asymmetry in the
920 Martian circulation and climate. *Nature*, 416(6878), 298–301.
- 921 Rodin, A., Korablev, O., & Moroz, V. (1997). Vertical distribution of water in the
922 near-equatorial troposphere of Mars: Water vapor and clouds. *Icarus*, 125(1),
923 212–229.
- 924 Shaposhnikov, D. S., Medvedev, A. S., Rodin, A. V., & Hartogh, P. (2019).
925 Seasonal water “pump” in the atmosphere of Mars: Vertical transport to
926 the thermosphere. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 46(8), 4161–4169.
- 927 Smith, M. D. (2002). The annual cycle of water vapor on Mars as observed by the
928 Thermal Emission Spectrometer. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*,
929 107(E11), 25–1.
- 930 Smith, M. D. (2004). Interannual variability in TES atmospheric observations of Mars
931 during 1999–2003. *Icarus*, 167(1), 148–165.
- 932 Smith, M. D. (2019). Local time variation of water ice clouds on mars as observed by
933 themis. *Icarus*, 333, 273–282.
- 934 Smith, M. D., Bougher, S. W., Encrenaz, T., Forget, F., & Kleinböhl, A. (2017).
935 Thermal structure and composition. *The atmosphere and climate of Mars*, 18,
936 42.
- 937 Stcherbinine, A., Montmessin, F., Vincendon, M., Wolff, M. J., Vals, M., Korablev,
938 O., . . . Baggio, L. (2022). A two martian years survey of water ice clouds on
939 mars with acs onboard tgo. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 127(12),
940 e2022JE007502.
- 941 Stiller, G. P. (2000). The Karlsruhe Optimized and Precise Radiative transfer
942 Algorithm (KOPRA). -.
- 943 Stolzenbach, A., López-Valverde, M.-A., Brines, A., Modak, A., Funke, B., González-
944 Galindo, F., . . . others (2023). Martian atmospheric aerosols composition
945 and distribution retrievals during the first martian year of NOMAD/TGO
946 solar occultation measurements: 1. methodology and application to the my

- 947 34 global dust storm. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 128(11),
 948 e2022JE007276.
- 949 Streeter, P. M., Lewis, S. R., Patel, M. R., Holmes, J. A., Fedorova, A. A., Kass,
 950 D. M., & Kleinböhl, A. (2021). Asymmetric impacts on Mars' polar vortices
 951 from an equinoctial global dust storm. *Journal of Geophysical Research:*
 952 *Planets*, 126(5), e2020JE006774.
- 953 Thomas, I. R., Aoki, S., Trompet, L., Robert, S., Depiesse, C., Willame, Y., ...
 954 others (2022). Calibration of NOMAD on ESA's ExoMars trace gas orbiter:
 955 Part 1—the solar occultation channel. *Planetary and Space Science*, 218,
 956 105411.
- 957 Trompet, L., Vandaele, A., Thomas, I., Aoki, S., Daerden, F., Erwin, J., ... Patel,
 958 M. (2023). Carbon dioxide retrievals from NOMAD-SO on ESA's ExoMars
 959 Trace Gas Orbiter and temperature profiles retrievals with the hydrostatic
 960 equilibrium equation: 1. description of the method. *Journal of Geophysical*
 961 *Research: Planets*, 128(3), e2022JE007277.
- 962 Vandaele, A. C., Korablev, O., Daerden, F., Aoki, S., Thomas, I. R., Altieri, F., ...
 963 others (2019). Martian dust storm impact on atmospheric H₂O and D/H
 964 observed by ExoMars Trace Gas Orbiter. *Nature*, 568(7753), 521–525.
- 965 Vandaele, A. C., Lopez-Moreno, J.-J., Patel, M. R., Bellucci, G., Daerden, F., Ristic,
 966 B., ... others (2018). NOMAD, an integrated suite of three spectrometers for
 967 the ExoMars trace gas mission: Technical description, science objectives and
 968 expected performance. *Space Science Reviews*, 214(5), 1–47.
- 969 Villanueva, G., Mumma, M., Novak, R., Käuffl, H., Hartogh, P., Encrenaz, T., ...
 970 Smith, M. (2015). Strong water isotopic anomalies in the martian atmosphere:
 971 probing current and ancient reservoirs. *Science*, 348(6231), 218–221.
- 972 Villanueva, G. L., Liuzzi, G., Aoki, S., Stone, S. W., Brines, A., Thomas, I. R., ...
 973 others (2022). The deuterium isotopic ratio of water released from the Martian
 974 caps as measured with TGO/NOMAD. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 49(12),
 975 e2022GL098161.
- 976 Villanueva, G. L., Liuzzi, G., Crismani, M. M., Aoki, S., Vandaele, A. C., Daerden,
 977 F., ... others (2021). Water heavily fractionated as it ascends on Mars as
 978 revealed by ExoMars/NOMAD. *Science Advances*, 7(7), eabc8843.
- 979 von Clarmann, v., Glatthor, N., Grabowski, U., Höpfner, M., Kellmann, S., Kiefer,
 980 M., ... others (2003). Retrieval of temperature and tangent altitude
 981 pointing from limb emission spectra recorded from space by the Michelson
 982 Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding (MIPAS). *Journal of*
 983 *Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 108(D23).